

Development of Students' Independent Study Skills Using New Pedagogical Technologies

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Abstract: This article considered the issues of developing students' independent learning skills with the help of new pedagogical technologies. Pedagogical technologies are new methods, tools and methods used to effectively organize the educational process and involve students in learning. Independent learning is the ability of students to seek and learn their own knowledge, solve problems, and adapt to change. The article analyzes the role of independent learning in student development and the contribution of new pedagogical technologies to the learning process.

Keywords: independent learning, new pedagogical technologies, interactive learning, digital education, student motivation, online education, innovative approaches to the educational process.

The main goal of the educational system is to expand students' knowledge, develop critical and creative thinking skills, as well as form independent learning skills. Today, the educational process is changing rapidly, and new pedagogical technologies play a big role in it. With the help of technologies, students are not only taught to acquire knowledge, but also encourage students to acquire and apply their knowledge independently, and allow students to manage the process of self-assessment and mastery.

New pedagogical technologies modern of students learning process relief and efficient organize to do directed method and tools is a set . These technologies the following own into takes:

Online education Platforms : Online education technologies to the students remote respectively knowledge get opportunity creates These technologies to the students own in time and convenience with learning , video lessons , interactive exercises and tests through to master makes it easier . For example, "Khan Academy", "Coursera", "Udemy". Platforms to the students lessons own at their pace watch to do and evaluation opportunity gives

Mobile applications and study programs : Mobile applications using students own knowledge independent respectively development can These are applications to the students to master Facilitator interactive tools , tests , quizzes , training cards and others offer does

Interactive education tools: In education interactive technologies apply of students activity increases and knowledge get process interesting does For example, interactive tablets, smartphones and tablets using students collective problems solution in doing active participation they will

Blended learning education) : Blended learning, i.e traditional lessons with online materials combined education model , to students himself development and independent learning opportunities present is

enough In this method students one of time in itself in class study and independent learning activities done they increase .

Independent learning skills development

Independent learning to the students himself organize to achieve, to the goal reach and knowledge in mastering responsibility to receive teaches. New pedagogical technologies using in students the following independent learning skills develops:

Planning and goal put: Readers education process themselves planning, purpose to put and to him reach for necessary has been strategies work exit they learn Education platforms and applications using they are themselves for planned lessons, exercises and tests according to the work

Time Management: Independent learning the time efficient requires management. New pedagogical technologies to the students own times in planning help giving tools present will , for example , study plans , reminders , time manage programs .

Himself Assessment : Students independent in learning themselves evaluation , results analysis to do and mastered knowledge again seeing exit they learn Blended learning and online platforms through students own knowledge tests using evaluation and the results analysis to do opportunity have will be

Creative and critical thinking: New technologies using students different different problems solution in doing creative and critical thinking they develop. Online courses and interactive platforms to the students problems solution in doing new approaches, alternative solutions and analytical skills to develop help gives

New pedagogical technologies using independent of learning benefits:

More mastering: Interactive and digital technologies using students the material more good they absorb Remote education and study programs to the students interesting and efficient learning opportunities present is enough

Motivation and enthusiasm upgrade: Online education platforms and interactive tools students to learn encourages , this while of students to education has been motivation increases .

Students independent respectively to learn Preparation: New pedagogical technologies using students independent learning for necessary has been skills develop and in the future own knowledge independent respectively more expand opportunity have will be

Summary by doing let's say new pedagogical technologies using of students independent learning skills development to the students own knowledge in learning and in application independent and efficient to be opportunity creates This is the process of students himself organize reach , time management , creative thinking and himself evaluation skills develops . With that together, new technologies education process interesting , effective and student for customized by doing creates So so new pedagogical technologies of education quality increase and of students independent learning skills in development big role plays

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